

RELAXATION OF THE BINDING ENERGY OF ELECTRONS WITH PHONONS IN METALS

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Abstract

The relaxation of the electron energy on the lattice fluctuations in metals is studied. The energy distribution of the electrons and phonons over states is considered to be equilibrium, so that it can be described by the Fermi and Bose functions correspondingly. An analytical formula for loss of electronic energy per unit time required to start acoustic oscillations of a lattice is obtained. It is shown that the magnitude of the power absorbed by the lattice is determined by the Debye and lattice ratios as well as by the ratio of the lattice and electron temperatures.

1. Introduction

Interaction between electrons and phonons is one of the main characteristics in the study of the fundamental properties of the physics of condensed media. A general theory of electron scattering on phonons has been developed by many authors; the main results can be found, for example, in the Ziman's monograph [1]. Different aspects of this problem in the case of bulk metals were studied in [2–12]. Fundamentals of the theory of electron–phonon interaction were developed in [2–4]. Electron–phonon relaxation plays an important role in high-frequency electronic devices [5, 6] and ultrashort laser processes [7], when electrons and phonons are in a nonequilibrium state due to a significant difference in their heat capacities. The unbalanced energy exchange between the electrons and the grating has been first theoretically estimated in [8]. In terms of practice, it is necessary to know both the electron temperature and the lattice temperature during the heating of the metals with a short laser pulse. To a certain extent, this problem can be solved by a well-known two-temperature model [9–12], which is based on two differential equations of balance of heat fluxes in bulk metals.

There is considerable interest in determining the change in the energy of the electron–phonon coupling when the volumetric metals are reduced to metal nanoparticles, metal islands, films, or clusters, where the particle surface has a significant effect on all processes [13–16]. It is caused by a more general physical problem: how are the well-known physical parameters transformed when the spatial dimensions of the metal are reduced and the surface begins to act as an additional diffuser? To solve this problem, it is primarily necessary to clarify the features of the electron-phonon coupling in the bulk metals.

In this paper, we propose a new approach to calculating the energy of electron–phonon interaction in metals. This approach makes it possible analytically to estimate the energy of the damping of electrons on the fluctuations of the lattice in a bulk metal depending on the temperatures of both the electrons and the lattice.

The paper is constructed as follows: general theoretical statements are given in the second section; Section 3 is devoted to the calculation of the change in the energy of electrons in collisions with phonons; and the last section contains brief conclusions.

2. General Statements

The interaction of an electromagnetic (EM) wave with metals will be studied in terms of classical optics. It is believed that every electron receives an impulse from an external field that accelerates of it movement, and for some time, which is referred as the lifetime τ , it moves freely. However, in the collision with the lattice, the electron velocity is lost, and excess energy is transmitted by the vibration of the ions. In this case, the creation and annihilation of phonons take place.

The efficiency of the energy transfer from the laser beam to the metal essentially depends on the mean free path (MFP) of the conduction electron in infinite volume l_∞ and on Debye length $l_D = \pi v_F \omega_D$, where v_F is the electron velocity at the Fermi surface and ω_D is the Debye frequency. The parameter l_D plays an important role in the energy exchange between hot electrons and the lattice. The values of this parameter for noble metals are given in Table 1 together with the electron concentration n and the Debye temperature T_D .

In the classical case of free electrons in the metal volume, the damping ($\gamma_b = \nu$, where ν is the frequency of electron collisions) is due to the scattering of electrons by phonons, lattice defects, or impurities, which, in general, reduce the electron MFP. In this case, the volumetric damping is commonly given as $\gamma_b = v_F/l_\infty$.

Table 1. Values of some parameters for noble metals

Metals	l_D (Å)	l_∞ (Å) [17]	v_F (cm/s) [18]	n_e (cm ⁻³) [18]	ω_D (s ⁻¹) [19]	T_D (K) [19]
Cu	1197	399	$1.57 \cdot 10^8$	$8.45 \cdot 10^{22}$	$4.49 \cdot 10^{13}$	315
Ag	1552	533	$1.39 \cdot 10^8$	$5.85 \cdot 10^{22}$	$2.95 \cdot 10^{13}$	215
Au	1968	377	$1.394 \cdot 10^8$	$5.90 \cdot 10^{22}$	$2.16 \cdot 10^{13}$	170

Volumetric scattering does not cause significant damping at high frequencies when $\omega\tau \gg 1$. Here, ω is the angular frequency of light and τ is the lifetime of the electron (or relaxation time), which can be estimated as $1/\tau = \gamma_b$. On the other hand, the contribution of surface scattering to damping is negligible only when

$$l_\infty / d \ll \sqrt{1 + \omega^2 \tau^2}, \quad (1)$$

where d is the particle size, and becomes important if

$$\omega\tau \gg \max(1, l_\infty / d). \quad (2)$$

To estimate the effect of electron scattering on the surface, the following empirical ratio is generally used [20–22]:

$$\gamma_s = A v_F / l_{ef}, \quad (3)$$

where l_{ef} is the effective MFP of electron and A is a phenomenological factor. However, this

formula can only be applied to the spherical metal clusters if the electron MFP l is smaller than their size.

3. Variation in the Electron Energy Interaction with Phonons by Collisions

Let us consider the scattering of EM waves in a metal with much larger dimensions as l . In this case, the collisions of conduction electrons with the lattice oscillations become the most important relaxation process and no other electron energy exchanges will be considered.

The irradiation of a massive metal at an initial stage leads to the heating of the electron gas inside of it. Since the time of establishment of equilibrium between the electrons after excitation is much shorter than the time of establishment of equilibrium between the electrons and the lattice, we can assume that the electron gas is in equilibrium, with the Fermi–Dirac distribution over the energy of an individual electrons; that is,

$$n_k = \frac{1}{e^{\frac{\varepsilon_k - \mu}{k_B \Theta}} + 1}, \quad (4)$$

where Θ is the electron temperature and μ is the chemical potential, which is determined by the concentration of electrons n_e using the expression [23]

$$\mu = \left(\frac{3n_e}{8\pi} \right)^{2/3} \frac{(2\pi\hbar)^2}{2m}, \quad (5)$$

where m is the electron mass.

It is believed that electron temperature Θ is much higher than the lattice temperature, which will be denoted by the letter T ; namely, $\Theta \gg T$. The maximum of the temperature difference between the electrons and the lattice, which defines the relaxation time of the electrons, is determined by the rate of heat transfer from the electrons to the lattice.

Let us calculate the amount of energy transmitted by the lattice to electrons per unit volume per unit time at arbitrary temperatures. In accordance with the standard method [24],

$$\frac{dU}{dt} = W = \frac{V}{(2\pi)^3} \int \frac{dN_{\mathbf{q}}(t)}{dt} E(\mathbf{q}) d\mathbf{q}, \quad (6)$$

where V is the volume of the crystal, the time derivative under the integral describes the change in the number of phonons per unit time in unit volume, $E(\mathbf{q}) = \hbar\mathbf{q}\bar{v}_s$ is the energy of the phonon with momentum \mathbf{q} , and \bar{v}_s denotes the speed of sound in the crystal.

Let $P_{\mathbf{k}_i, \mathbf{k}_i + \mathbf{q}}$ be the probability of transition of an electron from a state with wave vector \mathbf{k}_i to a state with wave vector $\mathbf{k}_i + \mathbf{q}$. In the case of interaction of an electron with a lattice, a phonon is generated or absorbed, while the laws of the momentum $\mathbf{q} = \mathbf{k}_f - \mathbf{k}_i$ and the energy conservation are fulfilled:

$$\begin{aligned}\delta\mathcal{E} &= \frac{mv_f^2}{2} - \frac{mv_i^2}{2} = \frac{\hbar^2}{2m}(k_f^2 - k_i^2) = \pm E(q), \\ 2m\nu_F \sin\frac{\varphi}{2} &\approx \frac{E(q)}{\nu_s},\end{aligned}\quad (7)$$

where ν_i is the initial electron velocity, ν_f is the final electron velocity, ν_F is the electron velocity on the Fermi sphere, and φ is the angle between the initial and the final direction of the electron velocity. The signs (–) and (+) correspond to the absorption and creation of the phonon, respectively. For about half a lifetime, the electron undergoes collisions with the radiation of the phonon, while the other half of this time is characterized by collisions with the absorption of the phonon. Considering the interaction of electrons with a lattice being linear in relation to the coordinates of the sound field oscillators, i.e., proportional to the displacement of the ions, then the probability of the phonon radiation is proportional to the number $N_q + 1$, and the probability of phonon absorption is proportional to the number N_q . In accordance with the energy conservation law, this probability will be as follows: $P_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}\pm\mathbf{q}}\delta(\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_i} + E(\mathbf{q}) - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_f})$. Thus, proceeding from the above,

$$P_{\mathbf{k},\mathbf{k}'} = \frac{\pi D^2}{\rho V \hbar \nu_s^2} E(\mathbf{q}), \quad (8)$$

where D is the interaction constant of an electron with a lattice, ρ is the mass density of the crystal, and $\mathbf{k}' = \mathbf{k} \pm \mathbf{q}$.

Let us find a change in the number of phonons per unit time, which appear in Eq. (6). According to the Harrison [24],

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{N_q(t)}{dt} &= \int P_{\mathbf{k}_i, \mathbf{k}_i \pm \mathbf{q}} \left[(N_q + 1)n_{\mathbf{k}_f}(1 - n_{\mathbf{k}_i}) - N_q \right. \\ &\quad \left. \times n_{\mathbf{k}_i}(1 - n_{\mathbf{k}_f}) \delta(\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_i} + E(\mathbf{q}) - \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_f}) \right] dV_{\mathbf{k}_f}.\end{aligned}\quad (9)$$

Here,

$$N_q = \frac{1}{e^{\frac{E(q)}{k_B T}} - 1}. \quad (10)$$

The change in the number of phonons in time in Eq. (9) is due to their creation and annihilation. These processes can occur provided that the electron velocity is greater than the speed of sound in the crystal. In this case, the "creation" of a phonon corresponds to the classical Cherenkov radiation. When the temperatures of the electrons and the phonons are equal, expression (9) becomes zero. Let us calculate expression (9) when these temperatures are different. Let us first explicitly express the expression in the square brackets of Eq. (9) in terms of the respective energy and temperature using the distribution functions for $n_{\mathbf{k}}$ and N_q and the law

of energy conservation $\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_i} = \varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_f} - E(\mathbf{q})$. After simple algebraic transformations, we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} & (N_{\mathbf{q}} + 1)n_{\mathbf{k}_f} (1 - n_{\mathbf{k}_i}) - N_{\mathbf{q}}n_{\mathbf{k}_i} (1 - n_{\mathbf{k}_f}) \\ &= \frac{1}{e^{(\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_f} - \mu)/k_B\Theta} + 1} \frac{e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B T} - e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B\Theta}}{e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B T} - 1} \\ & \quad \times \frac{e^{(\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_f} - \mu - E(\mathbf{q}))/k_B\Theta}}{e^{(\varepsilon_{\mathbf{k}_f} - \mu - E(\mathbf{q}))/k_B\Theta} + 1}. \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

Substituting this expression into Eq. (9), we pass in it to the integration over finite states in the space of quasi-impulses by the rule

$$\int dV_{\mathbf{k}_f} = \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^\pi \sin \vartheta \, d\vartheta \int_0^{k_{max}} k_f^2 \, dk_f, \quad (12)$$

where $k_{max} = k_F$ is the maximum momentum of an electron (Fermi pulse), and we take into account the property of the δ -function:

$$\delta(x^2 - a^2) = \frac{1}{2a} [\delta(x - a) + \delta(x + a)]. \quad (13)$$

As a result, we find

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{N_{\mathbf{q}}(t)}{dt} &= \frac{(2m)^{3/2} D^2 E(\mathbf{q})}{4\pi\hbar^4 \rho V v_s^2} \sqrt{\varepsilon_F + E(\mathbf{q})} \\ & \quad \times \frac{e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B T} - e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B\Theta}}{(e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B\Theta} + 1)(e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B T} - 1)}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

If we take into account under the root the equality

$$\frac{mv_s^2}{2} = \varepsilon_F + E(\mathbf{q}), \quad (15)$$

then the formula (14) is rewritten as follows:

$$\frac{N_{\mathbf{q}}(t)}{dt} = \frac{m^2 D^2 E(\mathbf{q})}{2\pi\hbar^4 \rho V v_s} \frac{e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B T} - e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B\Theta}}{(e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B\Theta} + 1)(e^{E(\mathbf{q})/k_B T} - 1)}, \quad (16)$$

which, with the precision to the sign in the denominator distinguishes it from the previously known expression from [8]. The difference arose from a number of assumptions made in [8], which greatly facilitated further calculations for the authors.

Knowing the dynamics of $N_{\mathbf{q}}(t)$, let us pass on to the calculation of the magnitude of absorbed power W and turn to a spherical coordinate system in Eq. (6). Using Eq. (16), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} W &= \frac{2}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{m^2 D^2 v_s}{\hbar^2 \rho} \\ & \quad \times \int_0^{q_D} q^4 \frac{e^{E(q)/k_B T} - e^{E(q)/k_B\Theta}}{(e^{E(q)/k_B\Theta} + 1)(e^{E(q)/k_B T} - 1)} dq. \end{aligned} \quad (17)$$

Here, the following replacement of variables is performed:

$$\frac{\hbar v_s}{k_B T} q = x, \quad (18)$$

and the equality of energy is used:

$$\hbar v_s q_D = k_B T_D. \quad (19)$$

In this case,

$$x = \frac{q}{q_D} \frac{T}{T_D}, \quad (20)$$

and expression (17) will be rewritten as follows:

$$W = \frac{2}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{v_s}{\rho} \left(\frac{mD}{\hbar} \right)^2 I, \quad (21)$$

where I denotes the integral:

$$I = q_D^5 \left(\frac{T}{T_D} \right)^5 \int_0^{T_D/T} x^4 \frac{e^x - e^{xT/\Theta}}{(e^x - 1)(e^{xT/\Theta} + 1)} dx. \quad (22)$$

Since the Debye temperature averaged for 39 metals is $T_D = 250K$, and the average electronic temperature Θ is 7500 K, then, on the upper limit of the integral in Eq. (22), the exponent (with the temperature ratio) reaches a value of $T_D/\Theta \approx 1/30$, and the exponent will be $e^{1/30} \approx 1.034$. Consequently, within the limits of integration, the multiplier $(e^{xT/\Theta} + 1)$ in the denominator of the integral (22) can be assumed to be equal to 2. Thus, with high accuracy, the computation of integral I reduces to the calculation of the integral:

$$I_0 = \frac{q_D^5}{2} \left(\frac{T}{T_D} \right)^5 \int_0^{T_D/T} x^4 \frac{e^x - e^{xT/\Theta}}{e^x - 1} dx. \quad (23)$$

It is obvious that, at equal temperatures ($T = \Theta$), $I_0 = 0$.

If we use the equality,

$$ze^{xz} (e^z - 1)^{-1} = \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} B_n(x) \frac{z^n}{n!}, \quad |z| < 2\pi, \quad (24)$$

where $B_n(x)$ is the Bernoulli n th order function [25], then the result of integration can be presented as follows:

$$I_0 = \frac{q_D^5}{2} \left(\frac{T}{T_D} \right)^5 \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \left(\frac{T_D}{T} \right)^{n+4} \frac{1}{n!(n+4)} \times \left[(-1)^n B_n - B_n \left(\frac{T}{\Theta} \right) \right], \quad \frac{T_D}{T} < 2\pi. \quad (25)$$

In the case of $T = \Theta$, $B_n(1) = (-1)^{-n} B_n(0) = (-1)^{-n} B_n$, where B_n are the Bernoulli numbers and $I_0 = 0$.

The calculation of an infinite sum with Bernoulli functions in Eq. (25) can be

complicated. Therefore, let us go another way. Using the value

$$I_s = \int_0^{T_D/T} x^s e^{-kx} dx = \frac{\Gamma(s+1)}{k^{s+1}} - e^{-kD/T} \times \sum_{n=1}^{s+1} \frac{1}{k^n} \left(\frac{T_D}{T}\right)^{s+1-n} \frac{\Gamma(s+1)}{(s+1-n)!}, \quad (26)$$

and identities [25]

$$\frac{1}{1-e^{-x}} = 1 + \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} e^{-kx}, \quad \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^n} = \zeta(n), \quad (27)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{k^n} e^{-k\frac{T_D}{T}} = e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}} \Phi\left(e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}}, n, 1\right), \quad (28)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{\left(k+1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right)^n} = -\frac{1}{\left(1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right)^n} + \frac{(-1)^n}{(n-1)!} \Psi^{(n-1)}\left(1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right), \quad (29)$$

$$\sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{e^{-k\frac{T_D}{T}}}{\left(k+1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right)^n} = -\frac{1}{\left(1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right)^n} + \Phi\left(e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}}, n, 1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right), \quad (30)$$

we find

$$W = \frac{q_D^5}{(2\pi)^3} \frac{v_s}{\rho} \left(\frac{mD}{\hbar}\right)^2 \left(\frac{T}{T_D}\right)^5 \left\{ \frac{1}{5} \left(\frac{T_D}{T}\right)^5 + \Gamma(5)\zeta(5) - \left| \Psi^{(4)}\left(1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right) \right| + e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}} \sum_{n=1}^5 \left(\frac{T_D}{T}\right)^{5-n} \frac{\Gamma(5)}{(5-n)!} \times \left[e^{\frac{T_D}{\Theta}} \Phi\left(e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}}, n, 1-\frac{T}{\Theta}\right) - \Phi\left(e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}}, n, 1\right) \right] \right\}. \quad (31)$$

Here, $\Phi(a, b, z)$ is the confluent or degenerate Cummer hypergeometric function, $\Gamma(z)$ is the Euler gamma function, $\zeta(z)$ denotes the Riemann zeta function, and $\Psi^{(n)}(z)$ is the polygamma function [25].

The analytical result (31) was numerically compared with the numerical integration of formulas (22) and (23). In the wide range of T/Θ ratios, we obtained a coincidence of results. The smaller the T/Θ ratio is, the better is the coincidence. In the case of $T \ll \Theta$, the polygamma function $\Psi^{(4)} = -\Gamma(5)\zeta(5)$, and we finally obtain

$$W \approx \frac{q_D^5}{5(2\pi)^3} \frac{v_s}{\rho} \left(\frac{mD}{\hbar} \right)^2 \left\{ 1 + e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}} \frac{T_D}{\Theta} \sum_{n=1}^5 \left(\frac{T}{T_D} \right)^n \right. \\ \left. \times \frac{5\Gamma(5)}{(5-n)!} \Phi \left(e^{-\frac{T_D}{T}}, n, 1 \right) \right\}. \quad (32)$$

4. Conclusions

The general formula for an energy transmitted from electrons to the lattice per unit volume per unit time for arbitrary electron and lattice temperatures is obtained. The formula makes it possible analytically to estimate the decay rate (or decay time) due to the scattering of electrons in a bulk metal. This result may be important for analysis of the transport and optical properties for an arbitrary metals and for a more accurate estimation of the electron–phonon coupling in the metallic nanoparticles.

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